

Elevation residual analysis with scale mosaics

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Abstract—This paper introduces two elevation residual indices, the multiscale low-lying index (MsLLI) and the multiscale elevated index (MsEI), for mapping landforms associated with bottomland and upland positions respectively. These indices use a scale mosaicking approach to represent index values at spatially varying characteristic scales indicative of the local topographic variability in the neighborhood surrounding each grid cell in the input digital elevation model (DEM). The indices were extracted from two study DEMs, one in a complex landscape dominated by past continental glaciation, and the other in a relatively simpler fluvial landscape. Examination of the scale mosaics and key-scale maps allowed for a topographic analysis of the study sites.

INTRODUCTION

Elevation residual analysis characterizes the relationship between a point on Earth's surface and the surrounding landscape [1] and is generally used to map local topographic position [2] and surface roughness or complexity [3]. These land-surface parameters (LSPs) are frequently used as predictors in a range of environmental modelling applications, including soils, vegetation, landform, and geological mapping. Selection of an appropriate modelling scale, or neighborhood size, is one of the key challenges in performing elevation residual analysis [1]. Gallant and Wilson [4] argue that scale selection should be based on matching the length scale of the process under study and suggested that the process scale will be equivalent to the hillslope length in fluvial landscapes. However, in complex landscapes and/or at larger spatial extents, scale selection is complicated by the fact that process scale is likely to vary. Many landscapes are shaped by superimposed processes operating at vastly different spatial scales.

Lindsay et al. [5] demonstrated how locally adaptive scale selection criteria (scale mosaicking) can be used to calculate

deviation from mean elevation (DEV), a common elevation residual LSP. Scale mosaicking is a multiscale analysis technique that allows for the representation of a LSP at a range of spatial scales within a single raster map [3]. A scale mosaic is a map of a single parameter (e.g., slope, curvature, topographic position, roughness, etc.), where the parameter is measured at varying spatial scales in different locations [6]. Each grid cell in a scale mosaic represents the parameter at a *characteristic scale*, or *key scale*, that accounts for the unique topographic setting of the site [3,5]. Characteristic scales are identified for a grid cell by finding minima/maxima in the *scale signature* associated with the site. A scale signature is the function that relates an LSP for a site to spatial scales across a range of tested scales [6]. Therefore, a scale mosaic can be conceptualized as a way of collapsing a stack of scaled LSP rasters into a single raster, where each cell takes a maximal (or minimal) LSP value from the stack.

Scale mosaicking has several attractive qualities. Scale mosaics can represent topographic properties associated with landforms of widely varying spatial scales in a single map. This makes them well suited to mapping in complex landscapes that have been shaped by multiple geomorphic processes operating at widely ranging spatial/temporal scales. Because topography is the expression of landscape process, selecting characteristic scales based on topographic settings is more likely to result in a match between the process and modelling scales compared with non-spatially varying scale selection methods. Having the ability to represent local and broad scale features in the same map also implies that scale mosaics have a higher information density than any single uniform scale LSP map sampled from a scale stack. Every LSP scale mosaic also has an accompanying key-scale raster, which maps the spatial pattern of selected characteristic scales. These key-scale rasters have the potential to provide additional insights into fundamental landscape properties (e.g.,

where are topographic properties dominated by local versus broad scale processes?). These properties of scale mosaicking led Lindsay [7] to propose the scale mosaic hypothesis, which states: *LSP scale mosaics based on locally optimized scale selection criteria can provide model predictors with denser information, that are better representative of landscape process scales and thereby can improve modelling performance.*

Newman et al. [8] demonstrated that any LSP can be calculated using a scale mosaicking approach. For LSPs that characterize surface shape at a point, e.g., slope and curvatures, scaling can be achieved by measuring the LSP across a series of scaled digital elevation models (DEMs) using a Gaussian scale space approach [9] to suppress topographic detail at shorter scale ranges. Compared with other LSPs, however, those associated with elevation residuals are particularly well suited to scale mosaicking because they are based on neighborhood analysis, i.e. they are measured using roving kernels, or windows, of varying size. That is, their scale dependency is inherent in their definition and how they are measured. In this paper we introduce two new multiscale elevation residual indices based on the scale mosaicking approach, the multiscale low-lying index (MsLLI) and the multiscale elevated index (MsEI). These indices can be used to characterize the extent to which a location occupies an anomalously low-lying or elevated position across a range of spatial scales.

I. THE MULTISCALE LOW-LYING AND ELEVATED INDICES

Local topographic position (LTP) is the general topographic property that describes how elevated or low-lying a site is relative to its surroundings. Measures of LTP either situate each grid cell in a DEM within the context of benchmark elevations (e.g., height above the nearest drainage, or percent elevation between peak and outlet) or by comparing a grid cell’s elevation to that of a local neighborhood of a specified size. The latter definition of LTP takes the form of elevation residual analysis, and common examples include difference from mean elevation (DIFF), DEV, and elevation percentile (EP) [1]. Each of these LTP measures can be represented using a scale mosaic approach [2, 5]. These scale mosaic versions of LTP measures have generally defined characteristic scales by identifying the scale at which the LSP value is either minimal (a trough) or maximal (a peak) in the scale signature. For example, DEV can be positive (indicating a location is more elevated than its surrounding) or negative (indicating that it is lower than its surroundings). The scale mosaic version of DEV, known as DEV_{max} [5], defines the characteristic scale for a cell as the scale at which the *absolute value* of DEV, measured across a range of scales, is maximal. The scale mosaic version of EP, which varies from 0-100%, identifies characteristic scales that are most deviated from a medial landscape position, i.e., the scale at which the scale signature is farthest from 50%, either above or below the medial reference point.

The property of representing both elevated and low-lying positions in the same map is somewhat problematic because a site

can be low-lying at one scale and elevated at another. This can result in sharp discontinuities in some scale mosaics, particularly when they are derived from very wide scale ranges (Fig. 1). It is for this reason that Lindsay et al. [5] recommended breaking wide scale ranges into smaller local, intermediate, broad scale ranges, allowing sites that flip from low-lying to elevated, or vice versa, to be represented in the set of smaller-range scale mosaics and reducing the prevalence of discontinuities.

Figure 1. An elevation percentile scale mosaic for a 10-m DEM of a site near Peterborough, Canada, derived from a scale range of 5-250 grid cells.

As an alternative, we propose separating scale signature minimum and maximum functions, creating a separate multiscale low-lying index (MsLLI) and multiscale elevated index (MsEI). To calculate these two scale mosaics, we must first specify a test scale range, defined by a starting scale (in grid cells) and scale sampling density (e.g. the interval between tested scales). While the test scale range can theoretically increase to the global extent, in practice, the upper bound occurs when scales approach the full extent of the DEM and no further increase in window size will yield meaningful variation. Even smaller upper bounds are likely appropriate. The measure of LTP used for MsLLI and MsEI is the difference from a Gaussian-weighted mean elevation ($DIFF_{Gaussian}$), effectively a high-pass Gaussian filter. For each tested scale in the scale range the original DEM is differenced from a smoothed DEM resulting from Gaussian filtering with a kernel size corresponding to the tested scale. The 2D Gaussian filter function is symmetrical and circular, even when measured using square kernels, which is an advantage of this approach, resulting in fewer windowing artifacts. The efficiency of the smoothing function is important for scale mosaicking methods because it limits the practicality of sampling scale space densely. Thus, our implementation of MsLLI and MsEI uses Kovess’s [10] fast almost-Gaussian filter based on constant-time (i.e., performance is independent of kernel size) integral image transform calculations.

Average $DIFF_{Gaussian}$ values derived from a DEM over a range of tested scales will increase monotonically. This is because average relief increases predictably with scale and this function is in itself uninteresting for our purposes. Instead, we wish to identify scales at which a site is *anomalously* elevated/low-lying across the

range of tested scales. Therefore, the high-pass Gaussian rasters derived from each tested scale is standardized by dividing $DIFF_{Gaussian}$ values by the standard deviation of the entire high-pass Gaussian raster. These rescaled $DIFF_{Gaussian}$ values are therefore z-scores and are unitless.

MsEI can then be calculated by identifying the highest rescaled $DIFF_{Gaussian}$ values for each grid cell and each tested scale. Sites that are not elevated across all the tested scales have a MsEI value of 0.0. Similarly, MsLLI is calculated by identifying the lowest rescaled $DIFF_{Gaussian}$ values; once found, however, this value is sign-reversed so that the index increases the more low-lying a site is relative to its surroundings. In addition to the scale mosaics, it is possible to track at which scale the maximum (MsEI) and minimum (MsLLI) values were identified for each grid cell, i.e., the key-scale map.

Our MsLLI and MsEI implementations are available for use in Whitebox Workflows as the `multiscale_low_lying_index` and `multiscale_elevated_index` functions.

II. CASE STUDIES

The first case study data set was a 30-m lidar DEM of a 68×54 km² area near Peterborough, Canada. The site is bounded by Lake Ontario in the south. The southernmost section of the site is the former lakebed of the once larger Lake Ontario and exhibits organized dendritic drainage patterns, including the Ganaraska River. The site has been largely shaped by the processes of past continental glaciation. The Oak Ridges moraine dominates the southern half of the site and large bedrock outcrops are present in the north. The central region of the site contains several lakes, the largest of which is Rice Lake. Numerous tightly spaced drumlins cover the southern and central regions.

None of the scale mosaics in Fig. 2 exhibit any of the sharp discontinuities observed in Fig. 1, which is apparent upon closer inspection. Instead, index values were found to vary gradually. MsLLI (Fig. 2A), calculated at a broad scale range of 250 grid cells to 978 cells, was highest for the former lakebed (south) and its superimposed river systems, the lakes (mid-section), and lowlands between bedrock outcrops (north). The corresponding key-scale raster (Fig. 2B) shows that characteristic scales at or near the upper bound of the tested range were prevalent in the former lakebed and modern lake areas, and that the narrower lowlands between rocky outcrops were associated with shorter characteristic scales. However, all tested scales were present in the key-scale raster (Fig. 2B) and are represented in the low-lying index scale mosaic (Fig. 2A). We calculated MsEI for two separate scale ranges, 0.03-3.0 km (1-100 grid cells) and 7.5-29.44 km (250-978 grid cells) (Fig. 2), to illustrate how the technique can be used to separate landforms of widely varying spatial scale. The scale mosaic derived from the shorter scale range is dominated by the numerous drumlins (Fig. 2C) while the moraine dominates the broad-range scale mosaic (Fig. 2E). Smaller bedrock outcrops are present in

Fig. 2C and larger outcrops are mapped in the northern sections of Fig. 2E. The outcrops, which occupy an intermediate scale range between the relatively smaller drumlins and larger morainal ridges, can be seen to occupy the upper scale bounds of the smaller scale range map (Fig. 2D) and the lower scale bounds of the broader scale range map (Fig. 2F).

Figure 2. Peterborough site A) MsLLI for the scale range 7.5-29.44 km, B) the corresponding key-scale raster, C) MsEI for the scale range 0.03-3.0 km, D) the corresponding key-scale raster, E) MsEI for the scale range 7.5-29.44 km, and F) the corresponding key-scale raster. Grey areas in the key scale rasters (B, D, F)

correspond to sites with no index value because it is not low lying (MsLLI) or elevated (MsEI) at any tested scale.

The second case study data set is a 1-m lidar DEM of an approximately 5×8 km² area located 65 km northeast of Grand Junction, Colorado. The site contains two wide and deeply incised canyons, with East Fork Parachute Creek in the south and East Middle Fork Parachute Creek in the north; both are tributaries of the Colorado River. Cliffs line the walls of the two canyons. Outside of the canyons, topography is also dominated by fluvial processes, with a high drainage density and abundant small, incised headwater valleys. Fig. 3 shows the patterns of MsLLI and MsEI derived from the DEM. Unsurprisingly, the canyon bottoms dominate the low-lying index map (Fig. 3A). The corresponding key-scale raster (Fig. 3B) shows how the scale mosaic approach adapts the selected characteristic scales to the varying hillslope length, from the widest canyons to the narrowest headwater valleys. The elevated index scale mosaic map (Fig. 3D) is dominated by the ridges between incised river valleys and the upper cliff walls.

Figure 3. Grand Junction site A) MsLLI for the scale range 5-455 (grid cells), B) the corresponding key-scale raster, C) MsEI for the scale range 5-455 (grid cells), and D) the corresponding key-scale raster.

III. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces two scale-mosaic derived LSPs for multiscale mapping of landforms associated with bottomland and upland topographic positions. These indices allow for elevation residual analysis across wide scale ranges in a way that is unaffected by the discontinuities that can sometimes impact other scale mosaic measures of LTP. By applying the indices to two test sites, it was shown that the indices can map landforms that occupy widely varying spatial scales within complex landscapes shaped by diverse geomorphic processes; furthermore, even in relatively simpler fluvial landscapes the scale mosaic method is able to automatically adapt measurement scales to varying hillslope lengths. Further work should explore whether the high information density of MsLLI and MsEI rasters can improve the performance of predictive mapping applications that rely on LSPs as predictors.

IV. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Funding for this research has been provided by the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada (NSERC), grant number 401107.

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